

DIAMAS Workshop: LIBER Winter Event

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Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

On Friday 2nd December, the DIAMAS project hosted an interactive workshop in Amsterdam, as part of LIBER's Winter Event. Our project partners, Bianca Kramer and Jeroen Bosman, of Utrecht University, hosted the 2-hour session.

The workshop set out to introduce DIAMAS and collect feedback from the librarians present about institutional publishing within their universities. In this first section, the audience were given an overview of the project, its aims, the consortium, and the organisation of activities.

The introduction triggered a discussion amongst participants, which saw those present share examples of how they would go about identifying publishing activities in their institution with support of the library. Bianca and Jeroen focused the discussion on an upcoming survey which the project will host, designed to map the landscape of IPSPs in Europe, collecting valuable feedback for libraries to contribute to DIAMAS.

LIBER is also an active participant in DIAMAS. The network of research libraries which it represents will be a key stakeholder group throughout the rest of the project. Research libraries are an important channel through which we can understand the landscape of institutional publishing and, later, will be a primary audience for the project's findings.

After the workshop, Jeroen commented: "Various participants stressed that they consider libraries as the go-to place to get information on publishing activities in their institutions. They also supported the idea that to leverage library knowledge, something like a 'pre-survey' of libraries should be used to understand institutional publishing service providers in their organisation."

Funded by
the European Union